

ARTISTIC AMATEURISM IS THE WAY TO LEAD COMMUNITIES.

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Abstract. This article describes the work activities of cultural center employees, the distribution of work activities of cultural center employees based on the regulations, and leadership of artistic amateur teams.

Key words: activity of center staff, tasks, tasks of staff, training. musical performance, status, dance, skill, amateur teams.

ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЙ ДИЛЕТАНТИЗМ – ЭТО СПОСОБ РУКОВОДИТЬ СООБЩЕСТВАМИ.

Аннотация. В данной статье описана трудовая деятельность работников культурного центра, распределение трудовой деятельности работников культурного центра на основании нормативных актов, руководство творческими самостоятельными коллективами.

Ключевые слова: деятельность сотрудников центра, задачи, задачи персонала, обучение. музыкальное исполнение, статус, танец, мастерство, самостоятельные коллективы.

2018 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of **Uzbekistan** Culture established by the decree No. 469-f of June 6 and from the investigations of the republican working group on the study of population recreation centers and the preparation of proposals for improving their activities, we can say that changes and additions to the sample staff table of centers, seniority and qualifications of employees who have been working in cultural institutions for many years it was mentioned that the procedure for payment of additional fee for the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations will be approved.

Development and approval of a five-year action plan for the exchange of experience and training of experienced and scientific potential specialists of the Ministry of Culture, regional departments and cultural centers abroad.

Training of specialists through the organization of activities of cultural centers, conducting mobile training and regional seminars aimed at preserving and promoting folklore, amateur art and intangible cultural heritage.

Creation of printing and reproduction of necessary educational and methodological manuals, collections, recommendations and other handouts for leaders and employees of cultural centers, clubs, studios and artistic amateur teams.

Organization of international scientific-practical conferences, scientific-practical conferences, seminars, master classes and experience exchange training-seminars on the topic of "further improvement and improvement of the activity of cultural centers". The employees of the

cultural center must fulfill their duties seriously. Tugarak leaders must inculcate loyalty to the motherland, loyalty to the country, etc. in the children's minds, regardless of which tugarak it is.

Establishing a republican commission for the attestation of the management staff of cultural houses and club institutions and, based on the main tasks assigned to the newly established modern culture and recreation centers, in a period of two months, the staff of the centers will be certified in a situation of high demand, determination and objective assessment. It is said that it will be carried out.

Taking necessary measures and providing support for the employment of employees who will become vacant as a result of the optimization of the number of cultural centers and club institutions.

Improvement of the educational standards, curricula and programs of directions and specializations prepared for the centers of culture and public recreation at the State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan, the Tashkent National Higher School of Dance and Choreography, the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan.

Improving the skills of specialists of culture and population recreation centers by conducting mobile trainings and regional seminars.

Involving teachers of music and art schools, general education schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges to conduct group classes in cultural centers on a contract basis at a maximum rate of 0.5.

Training, production, and pre-diploma practice of graduates of higher education institutions in relevant fields and specialties, as well as students of vocational colleges of culture and art in cultural and public recreation centers (internship) is emphasized.

The functions of the employees of the cultural center are defined in the "Regulations" of the cultural center. The duties of all the employees of the cultural center are specified in clauses, and the employees must carry out their activities on the basis of this Regulation.

Each center will have an annual calendar plan for activities aimed at fulfilling the main directions of activities related to activities. The calendar work plan is made for one year and must be approved by the head of the cultural center.

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Teachers of music and art schools, general education schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges are involved in conducting group classes in culture and public recreation centers on the basis of a contract at the rate of no more than 0.5 reach

Training, production, and pre-diploma practice of graduates of higher education institutions in relevant fields and specialties, as well as students of vocational colleges of culture and art in cultural and public recreation centers (internship) is emphasized.

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The plan includes activities aimed at preserving and promoting the rich spiritual and cultural heritage of Uzbekistan among the population, especially young people, organizing folklore groups, national craft workshops, studios, amateur clubs and, of course, for those with disabilities. It is shown that it is necessary to organize groups. Each tugarak leader is an accomplished expert in his field, aware of the changes taking place in Uzbekistan in the fields of culture and art, spiritual and moral development, and the growth of national self-awareness. It is necessary to have the ability to organize contests, exhibitions, festivals and contests that provide wide and full disclosure, attracting different segments of the population. Only then will we be able to train mature personnel in the future.

Only then will we be able to contribute to the enjoyment of the free time of the population, especially the youth, by covering wide segments of the population with the cultural and public services provided by the centers of culture and public recreation.

Circles, studios, courses, amateur clubs and artistic amateur groups organized in cultural centers directions are as follows:

Abu Ali ibn Sina said: "A person becomes a person only because he satisfies the needs of others, and others behave in the same way. Someone sows crops, another bakes bread, a third sews clothes, a fourth makes a needle, and everyone gathers to meet each other's needs. Because each person works in his field of study, and the employees of the cultural sector serve as the main factor in improving the ideology, spirituality, and outlook of the society.

Throughout the history of social development, one can observe different conceptual approaches to the category of "society". Social, philosophical, economic theories offer different interpretations of this concept. For example, atomistic theory views "society" as a collection of individuals and the relationships between them: "Ultimately, the whole of society can be conceived of as a delicate web of interpersonal feelings or instructions. Each specific person can be considered as being in the center of the web woven by him, directly connected with some people, and indirectly with the whole world.

According to the teachings of M. Weber, society is a collection of individuals, each of them strives to achieve their goals.

Meaningful organization of cultural recreation and free time of the population, especially young people, development of folk art, amateur art and comprehensive support of young talents, and also Uzbek national traditions through folklore art. custom, tradition

and the services of local cultural and population recreation centers are incomparable in preserving and passing on values to the next generation.

Many artists have grown up among the participants of artistic amateur clubs and teams organized in cultural centers. Also, singing and dancing, folklore, vocal-variety, status, askiya, curiosity, trumpet-trumpet, bacchanal, doormanship, circus, national instruments, visual and applied arts, folk theater and puppet theaters. The examination is being conducted according to the direction and at the festivals, talents whose names are not yet known to many people are identified, and positive work is being done to widely promote their creations.

Reviews, reviews that provide a wide and complete disclosure of the changes taking place in Uzbekistan in the fields of culture and art, spiritual and moral development, and the growth of national self-awareness. The main goal of organizing and holding exhibitions, festivals and contests involving different layers of the population is to discover new talented young people.

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